

Assessment of Social Factors and Promiscuity Among The Secondary School Students in South–South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria

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Abstract –The study sought to determine the relationship between social variables and promiscuity among SSS3 students in South–South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. Two research questions were raised and two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. A correlational research design was adopted while population of the study comprised all the 15,222 Senior Secondary One (SSS3) students in the 63 public secondary schools in South–South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. A sample size of 375 Senior Secondary One (SSS3) was selected for the study. A simple random sampling technique was used to select a sample size of 25 public secondary schools out of 63 as well as 15 SS1 students from each of the sampled schools for instrument administration. The researcher’s developed and validated instrument titled “Assessment of Social Factors among the Secondary School Students Questionnaire were used for data collection. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to answer the research questions and testing of hypotheses, all at the degree of freedom of 373 and at .05 significant levels. The findings further showed a high positive and significant relationship between parental upbringing, desire for materialism and promiscuity among SSS3 students in South–South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. Conclusion was drawn from the findings while the researcher recommends among other things that, school administrators, parents and teachers should wake up to their responsibilities of monitoring and advising students on the kind of associations they should keep, so as to reduce peer influences towards premarital sex.

Keywords: Product Moment Correlation (PPMC), Geopolitical Zone, data collection, SSS3, family discipline.

1. INTRODUCTION

Social factors are considered an important resource for physical, psychological and social well-being of students. Such variables may also exposed students to risk of engaging in promiscuous activities. One of the social variables which may influence students’ act of promiscuity is peer pressure.

Every one including the children needs law and order so as to behave well and be accepted by the society. The first place where children are expected to receive discipline is the family or the home. Children that come from homes where parental discipline are effectively enforced are likely to obey and comply with the rules and regulations superior authorities’ vis-a-vis that of the school, that forbids promiscuous activities. Henderson (2014) avers that children who learn to accept parental authority will also tend to behave in accordance with right pattern of behaviour and conduct expected of them in the school. Thus, if children who display bad behaviour at home are disciplined, such children may not carry-over such behaviour to school. Failure to discipline erring children at home may lead them to show deviant behaviour such as sexual assault and other promiscuous activities.

Exposure to video films, particularly those that contain indiscriminate acts of promiscuity may likely influence students sexual behaviour. As noted by Ward and Friedman (2013), exposure to pornography

predicted sexual uncertainty, less contraception usage, and earlier sexual debut. The authors argued that traditional media (television, radio, movies), as well as new digital media (the internet, social networking sites such as Facebook, myspace), play very crucial role in children's sexuality and sexual behaviours. This implies that greater exposure to sexually explicit television movies during adolescence were may likely encourage permissive sexual attitudes, higher expectations of sexual activities and more sexual experiences among students.

Therefore, it is observed that if an in-dept and critical study is conducted on social variables and promiscuity among senior secondary one students in South–South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria, will go a long way in solving some of the health related problems associated with premarital sex among students.

2. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- The relationship between family discipline and promiscuity among senior secondary one students in South–South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria.
- The relationship between exposure to video films and promiscuity among senior secondary one students in South–South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria.

3. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- What is the relationship between family discipline and promiscuity among senior secondary one students in South–South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria?
- What relationship exists between exposure to video films and promiscuity among senior secondary one students in South–South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria?

4. RELATED LITERATURE

4.1 Family Discipline and Students Promiscuity

Discipline could be described as ability of an individual to reflect societal values and expectations in carrying out activities as to when, where and how such activities are expected to be done. Ukegbe and Ken (2010) asserted that disciplined people do not talk about personal interest, but on what benefits others. They enumerated the following as attributes of discipline, namely: modesty, respect for the legitimate authorities, dedication, perseverance and more. Disciplined students are devoted to their academic work and other assignments or tasks given by the school authority

Udoh (2010) described discipline as good when both the teacher and the students obey the rules, and create a conducive and stimulating environment to enjoy their work and achieve the goals of the institution. The author maintains that both goals are interrelated and equally important, in recent years, the first goal (developing self-discipline) has largely been overshadowed by educators' focus on the second (managing and correcting misbehaviour) particularly in middle level and high schools.

According to Ogodo (2015), discipline is the training of the mind and character in order to produce obedience to rules, self-control and self-respect. The author explained that discipline is the process of training and learning which fosters growth and maturity. It helps people to be well behaved, happy and

useful to society. Bear (2010) opined that in order to foster discipline, parents are expected to understand and appreciate the difference between right and wrong, assume responsibility for their actions, recognize the importance of cooperative relationships, and show genuine care and interest in others.

Providing appropriate discipline to children is one of the most essential responsibilities of parents. All children need adults in their lives who will assist them to think before they act, to reflect upon various challenging situations, to realize the different consequences of their actions and to take responsibility for their behaviour. Isma'il (2010: 19p) stated, "Parental discipline involves teaching children the boundaries of what is acceptable and what is not acceptable; and to also make them aware of the values and actions that are acceptable in their family and society". Uson (2010) also noted that, discipline can be positive, for example, praising a child for doing something good or stopping something inappropriate, also discipline can be in negative form for example, smacking an adolescent for doing wrong.

Therefore, parents should design discipline to help adolescents engage better with others and be able to control their behaviours. Such discipline will make children be aware of values and actions that are acceptable in their family and society, thereby, reducing deviant behaviour among students (Uson, 2010).

Parents use different disciplinary styles in teaching children values and actions acceptable in the family and the society. Authoritarian disciplinary style is one of them. In this style of discipline, parents are neither frequently warm nor nurturing (Ali, 2010). They do not easily take their children's feelings into consideration and tend to be more rigid, imposing rules without discussing the rationale with their children. They resort to authority and basically seek compliance and obedience. Authoritarian parents are likely to resort to corporal punishment rather than a problem-solving approach, when they feel their children are not complying with their demands or have transgressed in some fashion.

The purpose of discipline is to encourage moral, physical, intellectual development and sense of responsibility in children. According to Adelson (2010), discipline has two functions, the first is to ensure that children have a consistent, safe and secure environment in which they can learn reasonable rules, limits and consequences, as well as to develop an understanding of why these are important. The second function equally important but, not as readily emphasized is to nature self-control. It is the responsibility of the parents to instill good discipline in children to teach conformity and obedience. Punishment serves to inhibit undesirable acts and rewards serve to reinforce desirable acts. Effective discipline is an act of recognizing deviant behaviours and keeping track of when they occur. Consistent discipline must be insured at the sighting of these behaviours in order to prevent the development. The child may view the punishment as unfair and unjust and this can cause them to act out. Crosswhite and Kerpelman (2018), noted that lack of proper discipline from parents at home increases the chances of sexual molestation among students.

4.2 Exposure to Video Films and Students Promiscuity

Video films displayed on television screen have great influence upon socialization of children, adolescents and even adults. According to Vasan (2010), exposure to pornographic movies can greatly influence youth's ideas of fashion, their choices of clothing and accessories. Therefore, it is important to know what kind of movies are being produced for consumption, since as a result of technology, more and more people in the society, have access to so many movies (Daramola, 2015).

Video films can positively or negatively affect the generally accepted moral standards of youth. Positively, home video such as television films and other motion pictures also create positive influence on the child

education and morality. According to Ibia (2009), the influence of home video is immediate since children see these live pictures as realistic and standards to be copied. Plays depicting honesty, love, sympathy patriotism among others, could be shown on the television screen which could lead to good behaviour formation. Children may even be asked to participate in dramatizing some of the plays. Formal lessons in English Language, Geography, History, Mathematics, Physics and so on could be taught to children through the medium of a television teacher. Special programmes could be designed in home video as children programmes, which could enhance quality child education and moral development.

Negatively, a number of academic researchers have addressed the influence of video films on children's behaviour formation. Onokome (2004) who researched on the influence of home video on students' behaviour stated that students' sexual behaviour and violence is one of the effects of video films. Children who watch a lot of video films with pornographic contents are prone to practice sexual behaviour outside marital union. There is the belief that people often accept the fictional representation in the media for their vivid and demonstrative relay of pictures. Ekwazi (2011) opined that when children identify themselves with admired actors and actresses who acted immoral films, they often copy such behaviour whenever a relevant situation arises. This is because children often perceive a particular link between media mediated fantasy and concrete reality.

In addition, Adieza (2008) noted that most video films depict sexually related behaviour and when children watch such movies, they are sexually aroused especially the adolescents and this could often lead to anti-social vices such as sexual addiction, lesbianism and homosexuality. Peterson and Kahn in Vasani (2010) noted that early initiation of sexual behaviour is promoted by exposure to pornography in video films. Escobar-Chaves, Tortolero and Markham (2004) added that exposure to video films with emphasis on sex and pornography increased the likelihood of having multiple sex partners, engaging in sex more often and soon.

5. METHODOLOGY

The correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population for the study comprised all the 15,222 Senior Secondary One (SSS1) students in the 63 public secondary schools in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. A sample size of 375 Senior Secondary One (SSS1) was selected for the study. A sample size of 375 will be representative of the population. Simple random sampling technique was used to select a sample size of 25 public secondary schools out of 63. A self-structured questionnaire that focused on assessment of social factors among the secondary school students in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria was raised. Questionnaire were distributed, and copies of the questionnaire were filled and collected instantly by the researcher to avoid loss of questionnaire. Data generated was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistics.

6. RESULTS

Research Question 1

What is the relationship between family discipline and promiscuity among senior secondary one (SS1) students in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria?

Table -1: Correlation analysis of responses between family discipline and promiscuity among SSS3 students

Variables	N	Σx	Σx^2	Σxy	r-value	Remark
		Σy	Σy^2			
Family Discipline (x)	375	5339	76127			
				73690	0.79	Very High Positive Relationship
Promiscuity among SSS3 Students (y)	375	5494				
			74718			

Source: Field data (2022)

Result in Table 1 reveals a correlation value of 0.79. From the decision rule, it is seen that a very high positive relationship occur between family discipline and promiscuity among SSI students in South–South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. The implication of this result is that students from highly disciplined home are less likely to be involved in deviant behaviour in schools and vice versa.

Research Question 2

What relationship exists between exposure to video films and promiscuity among senior secondary one (SSS3) students in South–South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria?

Table -2: Correlation analysis of responses between exposure to video films and promiscuity among SSS3 students

Variables	N	Σx	Σx^2	Σxy	r-value	Remark
		Σy	Σy^2			
Exposure to Video Films (x)	375	5426	76884			
				73553	0.74	Very High Positive Relationship
Promiscuity among SSS3 Students (y)	375	5494				
			74718			

Source: Field data (2022)

Result in Table 2 reveals a correlation value of 0.74. From the decision rule, it is observed that a very high positive relationship exists between exposure to video films and promiscuity among SS1 students in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. The implication of this result is that students tend to involved in promiscuous acts if they keep watching video films with sexual contents and vice versa.

7. HYPOTHESES TESTING

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between family discipline and promiscuity among senior secondary one (SSS3) students in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria.

Table -3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis of responses between desire for materialism and promiscuity among SSS3 students

Variables	N	Σx	Σx^2	Σxy	r-value	r-crit	Decision
		Σy	Σy^2				
Family Discipline (x)	375	5339	76127				
				73690	0.79*	0.196	Rejected Ho
Promiscuity among SSS3 Students (y)	375	5494					
			74718				

* Significant; $P < .05$; $df = 373$; critical $r = 0.196$ Source: Field data (2022)

Table 3 shows that the calculated r- value of 0.79 exceeds the critical value of 0.196 at the degree of freedom of 373 and at .05 significant levels. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, while the alternate hypothesis is retained. This means that there is a significant relationship between family discipline and promiscuity among SSS3 students in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between exposure to video films and promiscuity among SSS3 students in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria.

Table -4: Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis of responses between exposure to video films and promiscuity among SSS3 students

Variables	N	Σx	Σx^2	Σxy	r-value	r-crit	Decision
		Σy	Σy^2				
Exposure to video Films (x)	375	5426	76884				
				73553	0.74*	0.196	Rejected
Promiscuity among SSS3 Students (y)	375	5494				H_0	
			74718				

* Significant; $P < .05$; $df = 373$; critical $r = 0.196$ Source: Field data (2022)

Table 4 shows that the calculated r-value of 0.74 exceeds the critical value of 0.196 at the degree of freedom of 373 and at .05 significant levels. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, while the alternate hypothesis is retained. This means that there is a significant relationship between exposure to video films and promiscuity among SSS3 students in South–South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria.

8. CONCLUSION

Strong desire for material possession (financial favours and gifts) tends to strengthen students’ urge for sex out of marital relationship Students’ involvement in promiscuous acts is associated with parent inability to teach their children issues about sex as well as less discipline at home. The overall conclusion of the study is that social factors have strong connection with promiscuity among SSS3 students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Parents should take the discipline of their children seriously so as to help them develop good moral. Such discipline would also help the children to desist from nursing promiscuous desires.
- Parent should ensure that films with sexual contents are kept away from children and teachers should always give moral instructions to students on issues related to sex.

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